

Disconnection confounded at various stages of knowledge transfer from the academe to the hospital

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ABSTRACT

There is a recognized gap between the knowledge produced in the academe and practice in the health care institutions. An understanding on the elements that contribute to the disconnection confounded at various stages of knowledge transfer helps address the phenomenon. Hence, this qualitative research seeks to confirm the disconnection confounded at various stages of knowledge transfer from the academe to the end-users. It reveals that the success in the transfer of knowledge is linked to the policy and organizational environment support, dissemination and utilization mechanisms and dynamic interaction between the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and the hospitals. Thus, this research primarily confirms the disconnection confounded at various stages of knowledge transfer from the academe to the end-users are due to: (1) dysfunctional policy and organizational environment on both ends; (2) ineffective dissemination and utilization mechanisms; and (3) absence of the dynamic interaction between the users of research and the academic health researchers.

Keywords: *academe, health care institutions, knowledge transfer, dysfunctional policy, organizational environment, dissemination, utilization, dynamic interaction*

I. INTRODUCTION

The poor translation of knowledge from the source to the end users is evident in many settings. Between the academe and the health care institutions, there is a recognized disconnection between knowledge produced and practices in the hospitals. Knowledge translation (KT), as a multiplex concept, requires a thorough cognizance of its mechanisms, methods, and measurements. It also includes the factors influencing it at the individual and contextual levels. This also look into how both factors interact with each other (Sudsawad, 2007). In neglecting any of the processes, it

seemed unlikely that the expected benefits of the research will be realized. These factors may include the policies, dissemination strategies, and interaction between the academe and the health care system. However, a primary concern is the unequal dissemination of research efforts and funds directed towards the health issues of the populace. Such that, there is an imbalance in promoting the best efforts at ushering research to the health issues. (Delisle, Roberts, Munro, Jones & Gyorkos, 2005). Achieving research and innovation excellence in HEIs require breaking down existing barriers within and outside the institutions while building a collaborative and

entrepreneurial culture (Olupot & Maharaj, 2010).

International policy and research attention on how to reduce the evidence-practice and policy gap are increasing (Grimshaw et al., 2012). However, policies in the academe and hospital are not one in exhausting the potential use of research outputs. As pointed out by Cummings, Hutchinson, Scott, Norton, and Estabrooks (2010), research utilization investigators had called for more focused examination of the influence of context on research utilization behaviors. Likewise, Understanding-User-Context Framework for knowledge translation (Jacobson et al., 2003) also considered the domain of the user group on accepting numerous aspect of user group, such as the group's operational context, morphology, decision-making practices, entree to data sources, approaches towards research and researchers, and experiences with knowledge translation. Furthermore, ensuring that academic research should be available that can be utilized in supporting decision making and eventually advanced the value and method on providing healthcare services. However, Wilson, Petticrew, Calnan, and Nazareth (2010), revealed that what constitutes effective dissemination remained unclear. Thus, researchers required a vast and vibrant supervision in planning, resourcing and facilitating dissemination activities. Finally, the quality of the interactive processes between the stakeholders of the academe and the health care system helps improve the health care practice. Hence, it affects knowledge exchange critical in the assimilation of the new knowledge in advancing applicable practices in building a broader understandable context.

Undeniably, there are positive effects that research has already had in the area of health care and the advantages that can continue if research is continued in the industry. Although hospital evidence-based and feasible interventions are abundant recently, like treating pain from childhood vaccine injections, but still data show that more are not gaining this knowledge (Taddio et al., 2013). Brake (2005)

asserted that certain gap is present concerning theoretical knowledge and its practices. As agreed by Tomme-Bonde et al. (2013) that several attempts were done by Ministry of Health and Steering Committee to enhance and apply a collaborative, evidence-informed policy intervention, numerous obstacles were encountered in realization of the vision for core public health function operations, in early stages.

As the health care system is confronted with various challenges and equally important opportunities as it sets reforms, it must recognize that research plays significant role in approaching the various challenges and optimizing the opportunities for global development in health care. Apparently, there is a recognized gap in terms of the production of health research and utilization between the academe and the health care system, respectively. An understanding on the disconnection that starts at the production level and confounded at various stages of knowledge transfer from the academe to the end-users (hospitals) helps address the phenomenon. Moreover, determining the factors affecting the disconnection such as dysfunctional policy and organizational environment at both-ends, ineffective dissemination and utilization mechanisms, and absence of the dynamic interaction between users of research and academic health researchers also provide avenue for possible recommendations for effective knowledge translation strategies. Hence, this paper sought to confirm the disconnection starts at the production level and factors that confounded the disconnection at various stages of knowledge transfer from the academe to the end-users.

II. THE PROBLEM

The research aims to confirm the disconnection confounded at various stages of knowledge transfer from the academe to the end-users (hospitals) due to: (1) dysfunctional policy and organizational environment at both ends; (2) ineffective dissemination and utilization

mechanisms; and (3) absence of the dynamic interaction between would-be users of research and academic health researchers.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The study adapts the Canadian Institute of Health Research (CIHR) model (Sudsawad, 2007) of knowledge translation (KT) and the Research Utilization by Stetler Model (Stetler, 1994/2001) as frameworks in understanding and validating the phenomenon. CIHR model provides a universal frame of the holistic KT which inculcated resource information (production and application cycle). CIHR presented six opportunities within the research cycle at which interactions, communications, and partnerships which will help facilitate KT. These opportunities are the following: (KT1) defining research questions and methodologies; (KT2) conducting research; (KT3) publishing research findings in plain language and accessible format; (KT4) placing research findings in the context of other knowledge and socio-cultural norms; (KT5) making decisions and taking action informed by research findings; and (KT6) influencing subsequent rounds of research based on the impacts of knowledge use. On the other hand, Stetler Model of Research Utilization is adopted by practitioners as a procedural and conceptual guide for the application of research in practice. It is highly comprehensive and provides procedures to help guide practitioners in all steps in research process while considering the practical (utilization-focused) aspects of clinical decisions (Sudsawad, 2007).

In this context, it argues that at the production level of the research knowledge by the HEIs has significant impact on the utilization of health care professionals. Hence, alignment of the research outputs in the academe with their research thrusts and responsiveness with the needs of the health care professionals and administrators in the hospitals result to effective utilization. Such that, if aspects such as the development of the research thrusts and the development of the

research of the graduate students were given utmost consideration.

As the determinants of the disconnection of the knowledge transfer are given emphasis, effective translation will result. For example, policies and the organizational environment supporting research activities in the academe and hospital are necessary for effective implementation of the academic research knowledge. Meanwhile, research dissemination strategies implemented by the academe when appropriate, detailed to what the end users want to see and the quantity of information they can assimilate achieve effective research utilization. In addition, research utilization mechanisms in the hospital from the confirmation of the findings, its desirability for use, the actual use and the actual implementation process and subsequent evaluation when considered aids in simplifying safety and operative research findings (Stetler, 1994/2001). Finally, dynamic interaction between the academe and the hospitals that focused on their relationships if they have much trust and rapport, has history of working together with the desirable quantity and quality of contact lead to effective knowledge translation.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study uses qualitative research design to gather information related to confirm the influential elements of the disconnection at various stages of the knowledge transfer from the academe to the end-users at both ends. The elements included the policy, organizational environment, dissemination strategies, utilization mechanisms and dynamic interaction. It evaluated the influential elements. One-on-one interview was facilitated to the fifteen key informants who were included the academic and hospital administrators familiar with the research undertakings in the institutions. They were selected purposively in the two (2) College of Nursing Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and two (2) hospitals in Cebu City. The HEIs and hospitals included public and private institutions.

Generally, broad questions were asked on their experiences with the elements influencing the disconnection confounded at various stages of knowledge transfer from the academe to the end-users (hospitals). Probing questions were asked such as to provide concrete examples and particular situations related to the research elements. Specifically, it asked related questions such as:

1. Were there any policies supporting research knowledge transfer in your institution and what are these policies, if there are any?;
2. How supportive is the institution with regard to knowledge transfer and what are the kind of support extended?;
3. How are research dissemination strategies implemented by the academe?;
4. What are the existing research utilization mechanisms in the hospital?; and
5. How dynamic is the interaction between the academe and the hospitals?

Finally, the gathered information was transliterated and scrutinized using the constant comparison method.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The disconnection confounded at various stages of knowledge transfer is argued to be attributed to the policy, organizational environment, dissemination strategies, utilization mechanisms and dynamic interaction. Hence, this section presents narrative support provided by the academic and hospital administrators for each of the elements that contributed to the disconnection between the academe and the health care institutions in the knowledge transfer.

Policy. Policy serves as foundation for the accomplishment of the mission of any organizations. However, policies seem dysfunctional. Hence, these are not well-documented and institutionalized. Firstly, the key informant "A" in the academe mentioned that:

"From the graduate students, after they do their defense and comply with all the thesis and dissertation requirements, Activities related to knowledge transfer are not yet institutionalized or required to publish their papers. It is still in the pipeline..."

Secondly, another key informant "G" from the academe revealed:

"Policies directly related to knowledge transfer are not clearly articulated, but we have policies that would somehow relate to them...."

Thirdly, another key informant "H" from the hospital verbalized that:

"Policies related to the transfer of knowledge from the academe to the hospital are not yet developed. The ones who made the policies are the administrators who seldom have encounters with the students who produce the research outputs."

The results indicated that there are no explicit policies guiding the students in the knowledge transfer in the two HEIs to the hospitals. Although, there was the presence of the university research council which is a policy-making body for research development activities, programs and projects, this had not clearly described the policies related to the knowledge transfer. The absence of the written policy or document that directly reflects the knowledge transfer makes them dysfunctional.

Since there was no specific policy about knowledge transfer towards research of academic health in the healthcare institutions, health care professionals will have no guide employee in the participation in the use of research knowledge, identification of a violation policy, guidelines

indicating how and when employees will be allowed to participate and determined how the use of research knowledge will be structured with regards to on-going systems. In consonance to Crona and Parker (2011), policy makers who have strong connection to researchers are the ones who utilize researches more. Moreover, research adaptation are more likely embraced by other policy makers who are greatly influenced by. Thus, the scenarios contributed the disconnection between the academe and the hospital in the knowledge transfer.

Finally, the results indicated that when the policies that focused on the knowledge transfer are effectively functioning, academic health research will reach the intended users in the health care institutions. On the other hand, dysfunctional policies prevent the research information from reaching the health care professionals. Thus, the findings affirm that the disconnection confounded at every stages of the knowledge transfer from the academe to the end users can be attributed to the effectiveness of the policies

Dissemination strategies. There are variety of ways of the systematic distribution of the research information or knowledge from the academe to the potential users or beneficiaries in the health care institutions. As revealed, there were identified strategies such as research congress or conference and publication in journals. Motivations could be academic in nature directed by the organization or through personal desire to the target audience interested in the findings. The present findings supported Pellechia (1999), conference presentations and journal publications are traditional means of sharing research findings with other professionals.

As revealed by key informant "E":

"The students' output will be presented in the annual research conference after their 2 semesters of being enrolled in Nursing Research subject..."

In addition, publication in research journals of the institution was revealed to be one of the dissemination activities undertaken. Published research results can contribute to the knowledge, theory and practice of a specific field.

As mentioned by another key informant "M":

"The students' researches are published in our journal which is released annually. This is an area where we can showcase the research outputs of our students."

In congruence to Saracho (2013), research publication is very vital in academic requirements. However, doing such paper is quite difficult, especially the publishing process. From the strong support of Research Information Network and Joint Information Systems Committee (2009), researcher's output is published in all forms of publications and even web-based tools for social networking. However, there seems to be less dissemination activities undertaken which only included the two types of activities—research conference and publication. Meanwhile, whether the activities really achieved their objectives were not assessed. In addition, it is notable that the administration is still devising dissemination activities to deliver the research information to reach the intended users. With the dissemination strategies implemented by the academe, there is notably lesser avenue for the information to reach the intended users in the hospitals. Consequently, there will be less utilization.

Finally, proactive and reactive involvement and partaking of the health care specialist in the dissemination channels are less notable. As mentioned by key informant "C":

"We do not usually participate in conferences initiated by the schools...the only times where we could join them is if we are invited to judge the contests...or unless, our staff is enrolled in their school."

Thus, the findings affirm that the dissemination strategies have impact in the knowledge transfer. Hence, once there are more dissemination strategies that are varied ranging from printed evidence, electronic media and person contact implemented by the academe and participated by the end users, utilization will be high. In addition, the more favorable are the characteristics of dissemination strategies are, the higher utilization of the academic research utilization will result. On the other hand, the lesser the number and the lesser quality of the dissemination strategies, the disconnection at the various stages of the knowledge transfer is increased.

Organizational environment. With the increasing interest on the evidence-based practice in health, the hospital environment must be greatly considered. Hence, the use of academic health research in hospital practice improves the health care delivery. Organizational environment support may include hospitals' defined needs, time, resources and personnels. However, minimal support was gained in many of these aspects.

In terms of the defined needs that drive the organization to consider implementing research knowledge from the source must be clearly defined. Hence, the organization will be more likely ready to undertake initiative when it has objective information to support the need for improving specific areas [Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ), 2013]. However, this was not clearly documented in the hospital. As key informant "H" mentioned:

"In the hospital, there are needs to improve or sustain the practice but we have not studied them specifically. We have regular meetings with the executive committee but do not tackle much on how research findings from the students can contribute to solve those problems..."

Consequently, goals for the use of research findings were not also clearly defined. In addition, strategic plan was not created in relation to the use of the initiative. According to Citizen Services and Innovative Technologies of General Services Administration's Office (2011), strategic plan for the initiative identifies the resources needed and the appropriate metrics to success.

As further verbalized by another key informant "S":

"In here, there is no plan or program in initiating the use of research information from the academe..."

Furthermore, the adequacy of the support such as financial resources, time, staff support and capacity of the health care institution facilitate the adoption of the innovation in the current practices. However, minimal evidence gathered availability in the hospital which can enhance the research knowledge from the academe. As revealed by key informant "N":

"I believe that there is a very little support in terms of the staff and other needed resources for research to be utilized here in the hospital. It is an additional expense and staff are busy with their jobs.... no training or nobody is trained on that aspect..."

As supported by Ndinguri, Prieto and Machtmes (2012), human capital was a strategic factor in production (Son, 2010). It represented the cognitive competencies, skills, relational behavior and knowledge of individuals that enhance productive output (Shuller, 2000) that eventually contributed to organization's productive performance (Shuller, 2000; Son, 2010). Thus, this resource is necessary in the effective knowledge translation in the health care system. However, Alvaro et al. (2010) posited that conservation of resources theory contributed in

facilitating the use of research role, research use conflict and possible approaches to facilitate usage of research. Resources may account for the observed inconsistencies in research uptake across health professions.

As the Center for Health Dissemination and Implementation Research (2013) asserted that all departments (physical, staffing or financial supports) are obliged to carry out the outcome-based intervention. Wherein, sufficient resources response specifies that the study defines the physical, staffing, or financial supports is essential and proves that availability of resources are truly occurred. Hence, it is implied that health care system should effectively plan in the endowment of monetary fund requirements for the activity, appropriate scheduling, creation of supportive and facilitating infrastructures and sufficient workload or capacity as these are critical for the implementation of the knowledge translation activities. Thus, administrative resources are essential to research used within health systems.

Furthermore, Landry, Amara, and Lamari (2001) emphasized that the sources of funding influenced the use of knowledge as it is also true in this present study. In addition, the present findings also lend support to the view of Cummings, Hutchinson, Scott, Norton and Estabrooks (2010) that more positive contexts were associated with higher reports of research use in practice. These outcomes had effects for administrative endeavors to facilitate evidence-informed practice and maximize the quality of care. Importantly, the outcomes can also be utilized in guiding the advancement of interventions in modifying the characteristics of administrative context that are persuasive in modeling research use behavior. Similarly, recognizing characteristics of the innovation, organization, environment, and the individual were allied to research utilization (Dobbins, Cockerill & Barnsley, 2001).

Consequently, the results indicated that the hospital environment is not yet ready to utilize research information from the academe. Thus, the findings indicated that the poor quality of

the organizational environment support leads to a poor utilization of the academic health research in the health care system. Hence, this affirms that the organizational environment has a significant indirect influence on the knowledge transfer. For example, if there was clearly defined need, time, resources and personnel ascertained, the lower is the tendency for the link disconnection between the academic health research utilization by the health care professionals in the hospitals. On the contrary, the disconnection is increased if otherwise. Hence, the findings affirmed that the disconnection confounded at every stages of the knowledge transfer from the academe to the end users is also due to the organizational environment.

Utilization mechanisms. There are hundreds of billions spent on research in the worldwide. However, there is relatively little spent on how best to ensure that the lessons learned from research are put into practice. Consequently, healthcare systems failed to guarantee the effectiveness and profitable programs and services that they will gain.

Mechanisms must be directed towards phases of data application that include awareness, reception, cognition, discussion, reference, effort, adoption, implementation and impact. However, the researchers revealed that there was no mechanism developed for the health care professionals to utilize the academic research information in every stage of the ladder of utilization.

Specifically, health care professionals and their organization seemed to have no effort of learning about the academic health research. Retrieving a copy or accessing personally or through the institution was also not evident. As revealed by key informant "E:

"Although majority of the health professionals are aware of the existence of the academic health research, only very few had copy of the academe's health research or know how to access these health researches."

In addition, reading or planning to read academic research information is not demonstrated. Consequently, measures of modifying frames of reference, information influences action/adoption of information, influencing outcomes and results or effort to favor information, adopted information to become a practice and tangible benefits of information assessed were not notable. As key informant "M" added:

"We do not have identified and concrete means to utilize the research information from the schools. If ever we received research results, it is only very rare and it is only the initiative of those who have the interests on particular research findings to get a copy of it..."

Meanwhile, key informant "H" added that:

"The administration in the organizational level seems to have no desire of utilizing research information from the schools as if they do not care. As a result, there has been no effort that directs towards utilizing research findings particularly basing on the different stages mentioned..."

The findings of the study are supported by Beyea & Nicoll (1997) who noted that research application starts with passion in reading research papers. They suggested that research application in clinical practice settings, health care professionals such as nurses getting familiar and start reading research articles. Hence, some are overwhelmed by research, and others do not have time reading research reports. Lastly, reading research papers and utilizing research in clinical practice are very vital for all health care professionals such as the peri-operative nurses.

Moreover, the results agree with McKibbin (2005) that adaptation of research into practice and policy failed to realize. As an outcome of

these evidence-practice and policy gaps, patients fail to optimally benefit the developments of healthcare practices and the worse scenario they are exposed to gratuitous threats of iatrogenic harms, and healthcare personnel are exposed to preventable expenditure causing a momentous opportunity costs. Primarily, multi-tasking factor was indicated to affect the utilization of the health care professionals in the hospital. Hence, the health care professionals are focused to deliver quality health care services. However, use of this type of research information was less appreciated by the health care professionals.

In addition, it is affirmed by the study of Fetalver (2010) that for a mechanism to monitor and evaluate research utilization. Likewise, in consonance to Estabrooks et al. (2007), a significant variation in research utilization among health care professionals could be expounded primarily by differences in individual characteristics, with specialty- and organizational-level factors contributing relatively little by comparison.

Thus, the findings indicated that absence of effective utilization mechanisms which may be individual or organizational in nature influences the knowledge transfer. The absence of which negatively influences every stage of the knowledge utilization from the stage of awareness, reception, cognition, discussion, reference, effort, adoption, implementation and impact, respectively. Hence, the findings affirmed that the disconnection confounded at every stage of the knowledge transfer from the academe to the end users is also due to the ineffective utilization mechanisms.

Dynamic interaction. Interaction between the source of the information and the potential users is necessary for an effective knowledge transfer. Hence, on-going interaction between researchers and practitioners was identified as critical to knowledge being used in practice (Oborn, Barrett & Racko, 2010). In this study, the researcher revealed that between the source of the research knowledge and the potential end-users was notably less dynamic. Accordingly, dynamic interactions between the source and

the users may involve mutual engagement, involvement with change and ongoing contact.

Specifically, minimal mutual engagement is evident as the academe and the hospital enabled few irregular interactions among their members. As mentioned by key informant "G":

"The authors of the researches rarely have encounters with those who can actually use the research information produce or if and when they have encounters rarely mentioned about research findings which also seems to be irregular."

In addition, there is less support extended on the interactions, less involvement in the implementation of activities and in the dissemination of the follow-up activities. Another key informant "B" added that:

"It is only our personal effort to include ourselves in the activities where we could interact with them in the academe but not much with research.... it only happens if we continue or pursue graduate education..."

Meanwhile, in terms of the involvement with change, the academe and the hospital have minimal direct participation in the dissemination of research findings and in initiating the push for change. This was mentioned by key informant "E" who stated that:

"The schools just do what they are supposed to do such as the research conference to inform us of the findings and we can only participate if we are called upon or to act as external panel..."

Another respondent added that:

"Change resulting from the research

is difficult because innovations start from the society (group) who will determine whether to implement it and they (health care professionals) only act as mere followers..."

Finally, ongoing contact seems inadequate as the interaction with the initiators of change internal and external to the organization in terms of knowledge transfer was less. Mitton et al. (2009) identified that interactively engaging key leaders or champions is an important factor for successful Knowledge-Transfer and Exchange (KTE).

As verbalized by another informant:

"The interactions should be brokered or mediated by somebody in authority so that flows of information will be facilitated. However, this seldom happens as this is not the priority of many professionals."

Keown, Van Eerd, and Irvin (2008), argued that the potential benefits of including stakeholders in the process of a systematic review include increased relevance, clarity, and awareness of systematic review findings. However, the present results indicate that the fewer are the interactions undertaken between the academe and health care institutions, the lesser is the chance for the knowledge transfer. On the other hand, the more interactions that occur between the members of the two sectors, the greater is the chance of knowledge transfer. In addition, the quality of interactions must be emphasized. Hence, better quality interactions leads to a higher tendency for the knowledge transfer. Thus, the findings affirm that non-dynamic interactions contribute to the disconnection confounded at every stage of the knowledge transfer from the academe to the end-users.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The success in the transfer of knowledge is linked to the policy, organizational environment

support, dissemination and utilization mechanisms and dynamic interaction between the academe and the health institutions. Hence, as the quality of the policy that supports the various stages of the knowledge transfer increases, the higher is the tendency to continue to the succeeding stages. Similarly, the better the organizational environment that supports the knowledge transfer the more the knowledge transfer is facilitated. The more extensive is the support, the greater the chance that research information will be transferred. Also, success in research dissemination would likely lead to the use of information when utilization mechanisms are carefully planned and detailed, requiring time and support from the start to the end. Finally, the more dynamic the interactions are, in terms of the quantity and quality, the more research information will reach the highest level of the knowledge transfer. Therefore, this study confirmed that the disconnection starts at the production level and confounded at various stages of knowledge transfer from the academe to the end-users (hospitals) due to: (1) dysfunctional policy and organizational environment at both ends; (2) ineffective dissemination and utilization mechanisms; and (3) absence of the dynamic interaction between the users of research and the academic health researchers.

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